

Effect of Polarity on the Solubilities of some Organic Acids.

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It has been claimed by Walden (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, **55**, 703) that the solubility of a salt in a series of solvents is greater, the greater the degree of dissociation, *i e.*, the more marked the polar character.

The dielectric constant is the most direct evidence of polarity. The magnitude of this constant, therefore, indicates the moment of the polar groups within the liquids or the displacement of electrons or both. The electric moment depends upon both the magnitude of the charge and the length of the dipole.

In order to establish a relationship between the polarities of the solvents and the solutes, it is essential that a systematic study of the solubilities of substances with increasing polarity in a series of solvents of decreasing polarity should be made. Much data which are found in the literature are rather inadequate from this point of view and therefore the present work was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Conductivity water was used throughout the work. The organic solvents were purified by distillation at their known boiling points, whereas the solutes were twice recrystallised. Jena glass materials were used in the experiments and before their use they were thoroughly washed with chromic acid, rinsed with conductivity water and finally steamed.

Procedure.—100 C.c. of the solvents were saturated with organic acids in a series of flasks, which were kept revolving on a wheel in an air thermostat at 28° for 48 hours. At the end, the solutions were filtered. In order to avoid any error due to the absorption of the solute by the filter paper, 100 c.c. of a fresh saturated solution were filtered through it before the solution used for the estimation of the acid was passed through. As the undissolved acid

did not completely settle down, it was found impossible to pipette out a certain amount from the flask itself. A suitable amount of the filtrate was then titrated against $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ solution using phenolphthalein as an indicator. It was found by blank experiments that this method gave very reliable results, the error being less than 0.5%. Three readings were taken in each case and the mean was taken. Before the beginning of the experiments, the stock-solution of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ which was made free from any insoluble carbonate, was titrated against a standard solution of succinic acid. The hydroxide solution was also protected from being contaminated by air during the experimental work.

In the following tables, the solubilities are expressed in four different ways, *viz.* (i) in g./100 c.c. of the saturated solution, (ii) g./100 g. of the saturated solution, (iii) g./100 g. of the solvent, and (iv) in mol-fractions.

The densities of the saturated solutions were measured by means of a pycnometer. The densities taken are the mean of the three readings. The solubility in mol-fraction is calculated by the following:

$$\text{Mol-fraction} = N = \frac{n_1}{n_1 + n_2}, \text{ where } n_1 \text{ is the number of mols of the}$$

solute in solution and n_2 is the number of mols of the solvent in solution.

The ideal solubility was calculated from the following equation (Hildebrand, "Solubility" 1924)

$$\log N = \frac{-L_f}{4.58} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_m} \right)$$

N is the solubility of mol-fraction, L_f is the heat of fusion of the solute, T is the absolute temperature at which the ideal solubility is calculated, T_m is the absolute temperature of the melting points of the pure solute.

In the following table, the solubilities of benzoic, salicylic, phthalic, succinic and cinnamic acids in terms of "mol fractions" and the dielectric constants at 25° of the various organic solvents are given. The latter values have been taken from Landolt-Bornstein "Tabellen" and also from Dobrosserdow (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **41**, 1164, 1385).

TABLE I.
Solubilities of different solutes in various solvents in "mol fractions" at 25°.

Solvent.	Dielectric const. at 25°.	Solubility of benzoic acid.	Solubility of salicylic acid.	Solubility of phthalic acid.	Solubility of succinic acid.	Solubility of cinnamic acid.
Water	81.00	0.0005665	0.0003118	0.0008724	0.01460	0.0000894
Hexane	1.85	0.01399	0.00111	—	—	—
Carbon tetrachloride	2.21	0.0583	0.008603	0.0002244	0.0000118	0.01071
Benzene	2.27	0.08191	0.005441	0.0000447	0.00002924	0.03033
Toluene	2.34	0.08553	0.006752	0.0000469	0.0000209	0.02960
<i>m</i> -Xylene	2.35	0.0889	0.006524	0.0000465	0.0000304	0.02852
Chlorobenzene	11.0	0.1047	0.007903	0.0000577	0.0000176	0.03668
Nitrobenzene	36.0	0.1081	0.02809	0.0000698	0.000128	0.01463
Chloroform	5.1	0.1485	0.02679	0.000184	0.000138	0.07268
Methyl alcohol	32.0	0.1689	0.1252	0.05125	0.05620	0.06337
Ethyl alcohol	25.0	0.1882	0.1479	0.04265	0.04865	0.07605
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	22.0	0.1810	0.1488	0.02732	0.03613	0.0850
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	19.2	0.1968	0.1698	0.02231	0.02718	0.06156
Acetone	21.0	0.2141	0.1906	0.02596	0.02948	0.11930

The solubilities of different acids were calculated in g. per 100 c.c. solution and also in g. per 100 g. of the solution. However, it was noticed that these methods of calculation did not show any sign of uniformity when they were compared with the dielectric constants of the organic solvents. Thus, it was realised that before any comparative study of the solubilities of different substances is attempted, it is advisable to select only one method for expressing solubilities. Hildebrand ("Solubility" New York, 1924) rightly believes that "a gram molecule or mol has always greater significance to the chemist than any other of the amount of a substance." Greater importance is, therefore, attached in this paper to the solubilities expressed in mol fractions and they are made the basis for the subsequent interpretation of the results.

In Table I are given the solubilities of benzoic acid in fourteen solvents of varying polarities. As the solute is partly polar and partly non-polar, it will be expected that its solubility will be less in highly polar and non-polar solvents and greater in the intermediate solvents. The ideal solubility is reached in ethyl alcohol. It can be seen from the table that the order of the solubilities in different solvents is in accord with their dielectric constants. However, chloroform and normal butyl alcohol show an exception to the general behaviour. This is due to the fact that chloroform forms complexes with ether-oxygen and carboxyl-oxygen (Hildebrand, "solubility," 1924, p. 158) and therefore it acts as a better solvent than would otherwise be expected. In the case of butyl alcohol, the ideal solubility seems to have been exceeded on account of the formation of loose complexes with the solute.

The solubilities of salicylic, phthalic, succinic and cinnamic acids in all the fourteen solvents are also given in Table I. Their polarity is in the following decreasing order:—

Succinic acid $\succ$ phthalic acid $>$ salicylic acid $\succ$ cinnamic acid $>$ benzoic acid.

From the results obtained, it can be seen that the solubilities of different substances in solvents of varying degrees of polarity, as evidenced by their dielectric constants, are in accordance with their polarity and that of the organic solvents.

From the order of the polarity of the solutes, it will be expected that their solubilities in non-polar solvents, such as hexane, carbon tetrachloride and others, will be greater as one passes from succinic acid to benzoic acid. Secondly, in accordance with the polarity of

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these solvents, as seen from their dielectric constants the solubilities of the different solutes should increase, the order being:—

Hexane < carbon tetrachloride < benzene < toluene < *m*-xylene.

These expectations are fulfilled, as can be seen from the table, except in the case of cinnamic acid, where the order of the solvent action of the aromatic hydrocarbons is reversed.

In accordance with their polarity, the ideal solubilities of the acids will be reached either in methyl or methyl alcohol. Comparing their solubilities in methyl alcohol, the following order is obtained:—

Phthalic < succinic < cinnamic < salicylic < benzoic acid.

This is truly very strange. However, these results can be clearly explained if it is assumed that the last three acids become associated with or form loose alcoholates with the solvents, whereas the first two do not.

As mentioned above, it should be expected that the solubilities of all the acids in water should be less than those in nitrobenzene. From the table, it can be seen that this expectation is fulfilled by the solubilities of benzoic, cinnamic and salicylic acids, while those of phthalic and succinic acids are greater in water than those in nitrobenzene. This can only happen if these two acids become associated with water. Oxalic acid being more polar than succinic acid, crystallises with two molecules of water from its aqueous solution. It is, therefore, not unreasonable to assume that phthalic acid with two adjacent carboxyl groups and succinic acid with two carboxyl groups separated by the two methylene ones, should form hydrates with water, which may not be stable enough to be separated.

Thus, it can be seen that the solubility as expressed in mol-fraction of any solute is largely dependent upon the mutual polarity.

From the above study, predictions of solubility can be made. Thus, one can say that the acids studied will be more soluble in heptane, octane or nonane than in hexane, as the dielectric constant of the latter is smaller than that of any one of the former. Their solubilities in bromoform, ethyl chloride, ethyl ether, terpineol and bromobenzene will be less than those in either methyl or ethyl alcohol. Glycol, being more polar than nitrobenzene, will be a poorer solvent for all the acids studied, whereas aniline, which is slightly polar and more basic, should be a better solvent than nitrobenzene. Pyridine, being more polar, will be a better solvent than piperidine

and quinoline. The solubilities of the acids will increase with the higher homologues of benzene

The order of the solubilities of different acids in comparatively non-polar solvents can also be predicated with a fair degree of accuracy, depending upon the polar nature of solute. The greater the increase in the number of the polar substituents, such as OH, NO₂, NH₂, COOH, in the substituted benzoic acids, the less is the solvent action of non-polar liquids.

Predictions of the solubility in more polar solvents, such as alcohols and others, are beset with difficulties on account of the fact that many times 'solvates' are formed. However, one can say that if the ideal solubility is reached in ethyl alcohol, its higher homologues will be poorer solvents as well as methyl alcohol.

SUMMARY.

1. The solubilities of benzoic, cinnamic, salicylic, phthalic and succinic acids have been determined in fourteen solvents of varying degrees of polarity.

2. It has been shown that the expression of solubility in mol-fraction is a more rational method.

3. It is found that the solubilities in very slightly polar solvents decrease with increasing polarity of the solute, the solubilities of phthalic and succinic acids being negligible in these solvents.

4. The order of solubility is in accordance with the polarity of the solvents in the case of the aromatic hydro carbons, hexane and carbon tetrachloride, while in the case of more polar substances, the order is not well defined.

5. It is found that chloroform behaves abnormally with all solutes, while acetone and *n*-butyl alcohol do so in some cases.

6. It has been inferred from the solubilities of acids in water, nitrobenzene and alcohols, that benzoic, cinnamic and salicylic acids form loose 'alcoholates' with the solvents, whereas succinic and phthalic acids form hydrates with water.

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